

INSTILLING INTEREST IN MATHEMATICS IN CHILDREN FROM AN EARLY AGE**Barotaliyeva Dinorabonu Murodali kizi**

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Abstract. This article talks about the goals and tasks of teaching mathematics in preschool and general secondary schools, modern methods and interest of children in this field from a young age.

Keywords: "king of science", finance, computer technology, various shapes, strategy games, Lego toys, logical thinking, chess, interesting materials, extra classes, pedagogical skills, educational tools.

ПРИВИВАТЬ ИНТЕРЕС К МАТЕМАТИКЕ У ДЕТЕЙ С РАННЕГО ВОЗРАСТА

Аннотация. В данной статье рассказывается о целях и задачах обучения математике в дошкольных и общеобразовательных школах, современных методах и интересе детей к этой области с раннего возраста.

Ключевые слова: «король науки», финансы, компьютерные технологии, различные фигуры, игры-стратегии, игрушки «Лего», логическое мышление, шахматы, интересные материалы, дополнительные занятия, педагогическое мастерство, учебные пособия.

INTRODUCTION

Knowledge of the basic laws of mathematics is necessary for almost everyone today. Many professions are directly related to mathematics: finance, computer technology, engineering, etc. That is why, although it is not easy, it is very important to teach our children the "king of science".

Most parents probably agree that a child's first interest in mathematics appears during the process of assembling a constructor. Children especially love Lego toys. Lego helps them understand how to make large and complex devices from small parts.

RESEARCH METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

A great mathematician said that he became interested in geometry after his parents took him to an origami club during his school days. Indeed, this ancient art embodies most of the theorems of geometry, and the child's interest in geometry increases while making various shapes from paper.

Strategy games play an important role in the development of analysis and logical thinking in children. Such as checkers and chess games. It is a very good effect on the child's brain activity. Checkers is the most interesting, effective and simple game for preschoolers. Chess is relatively more complicated. The main task of teaching mathematics in a comprehensive school mathematics that students need in everyday life and professional activities that the system of knowledge and skills is acquired firmly and consciously is to provide. It is known that the majority of schoolchildren with a high interest in mathematics in elementary grades after higher grades, this interest decreases more and more. This is on the one hand due to the increasing complexity of mathematics programs, on the other hand, to increase the interest of teachers and students using additional interesting materials within the program the reason is his laziness

Based on my experience, I am witnessing that students are interested in this subject is increasing. This is exactly what happens to my students who come to my extra classes. Time is fast

technology is changing and developing. In line with this, students are especially. The interest of 1-6 graders in mathematics is increasing. In the upper grades as the topics become more complex, children move away from this subject. That's it however, it is demonstrative if the teacher's pedagogical skills are high with the help of educational tools, an interesting lesson can be held.

RESEARCH RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Today, both the teacher and the student are required to be able to widely use modern technologies and organize the lesson through them in interesting ways.

Visual aids are also one of the most effective methods. especially for elementary school students, colorful beautiful and antique things will not escape their attention

Mathematics is an interesting and unusual subject. And interesting mathematics sharpens a person's mind and helps to solve problems encountered in everyday life more easily.

Studying exact sciences has always been considered difficult, this process requires strong patience and will from a person. In our educational center, a consistent and effective program has been developed for the study of mathematics, among other subjects.

In mathematics lessons, each student is approached individually, because everyone's ability to receive is different. Someone completes all tasks at home on time, while someone stops halfway through the examples and gets stuck. For this reason, an individual approach is used and it has been effective for many years.

CONCLUSION

Knowledge of mathematics strengthens the memory. Scientists from Stanford University in the USA have studied the process of human processing of mathematical problems and have come to the conclusion that mathematics strengthens memory.

Math builds character. Solving math problems correctly requires concentration, stamina, responsibility, precision, and order. A lot of work of these instincts leads to their strengthening, which is very useful not only in solving problems, but also in solving life problems.

In conclusion, as mathematics advances, so does every other field. if work is carried out with precision in each field, if planned work is done, it will not fail to show its results.

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